

ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF NANOCELLULOSE ADDITIVES IN PORTLAND CEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Nanocellulose additives can improve the strength and durability of concrete; however, their economic and environmental impact on the production of cementitious building materials is not well documented. In this study, the cost and global warming potential (GWP) attributed to producing a nanocellulose-Portland cement (PC) composite material is evaluated using current costs provided by manufacturers and cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment data. The results show that a 0.2% volume nanocellulose-PC composite has a cost between 43.49% to 836.84%, and a GWP between -0.15% to 119.72%, of that of PC, depending on the type of nanocellulose used.

KEYWORDS

Composite Building Materials; Portland Cement Composites; Nanocellulose; Life Cycle Assessment

INTRODUCTION

The production of cement is responsible for up to 8% of global greenhouse gas emissions each year, leading to a demand for more sustainable cementitious mixes in the construction industry (Andrew, 2019). Additionally, concrete is one of the most consumed materials on earth, second only to water, meaning the cost per kg of a concrete mix can determine whether it is employed commercially, regardless of its GWP. Thus, performance-enhancing additives for concrete mixes should be considered for their impact on the environmental and economic performance of the composite material before they are employed commercially. Although low volumes of additives like nanocellulose are typically used, their addition to the mix can alter the environmental impact of the resulting concrete composite material over its lifecycle. Additionally, their cost must be considered as these additives tend to be produced at smaller scales and can therefore be more expensive than PC alone. Thus, the analysis of the economic and environmental impact of performance-enhancing additives can aid in the industry adoption of more sustainable cementitious materials.

Cellulose is an abundant and widely available material that can be extracted from a variety of biomaterial feedstocks, like trees and grasses, as well as recycled from waste streams. As a natural, renewable material, it sequesters carbon dioxide during its lifetime that can be locked into building materials, essentially creating a carbon sink. This effect is quantified by measuring the biogenic carbon of a material, which considers the biogenic landscape and process attributes that contribute to either the production or sequestration of carbon associated with their growth (United States Environmental Protection Agency & Office of Atmospheric Programs, 2014).

The addition of nanocellulose to concrete has been shown to increase its flexural strength by up to 50% and improve other mechanical properties like compressive strength and hardness (Cao et al., 2016; Hisseine et al., 2019). It can also improve the durability performance of concrete, such as chloride penetration, water absorption, and freeze-thaw damage resistance (Aziz et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2020), as well as reduce shrinkage and improve hydration (Guo et al., 2020; Hisseine et al., 2020). These improvements could be an overall benefit to the sustainability and cost of the concrete due reduced material usage, longer service life, and less maintenance. However, the positive impacts of these performance enhancements, including carbon sequestration, can be offset by the amount of electricity and chemicals required to process biomaterial feedstocks into nanocellulose.

While life cycle assessments have evaluated the GWP of various types of nanocellulose alone, little is known about the impact of nanocellulose additives on the sustainability of cement. In this study, the economic and environmental impact of nanocellulose additives in cementitious materials is evaluated through a literature review of GWP from cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment data, as well as costs currently available from nanocellulose manufacturers. This first assessment is crucial in understanding which parameters affect the cost and GWP of nanocellulose-PC materials the most during the production, and therefore which variables should be analyzed further for cost and sustainability optimization in future commercialization.

METHODS

In this study, the GWP and cost of 1 kg of PC is compared to that of 1 kg of a nanocellulose-PC composite material. The composite material is comprised of 99.8% PC by volume, and 0.2% nanocellulose by volume. This concentration of nanocellulose in the cement paste was shown by Cao et. al. to provide the maximum strength increase when compared to plain cement (Cao et al., 2016). In concentrations higher than 0.2% volume, nanocellulose tends to agglomerate, and thus the strength begins to decline (Cao et al., 2016). Hence, this volume concentration is used for comparison with plain PC in this study.

Two types of nanocellulose were reviewed: cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) and cellulose nanofibers (CNF). The cost and GWP of both PC and nanocellulose are reported here in mass (kg). Consequently, calculating the GWP and cost of the composite material required conversion of mass to volume. A specific gravity (SG) of 3.15 for cement (Mix Design and Test Methods, 2014), a density of 1.6 g/cm³ for CNC (R. J. Moon et al., 2011), and a density of 1.5 g/cm³ for CNF (Ansari & Berglund, 2016) was applied for this conversion. A composite density was then calculated for the nanocellulose-PC composite for each nanocellulose type using the following equation:

$$\rho_{composite} = (0.998)(SG_{cement}) + (0.002)(\rho_{nanocellulose}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

This density was used to calculate the GWP and cost of 1 kg of nanocellulose-PC composite once the volumetric results of cost and GWP were summed.

Global Warming Potential

The most effective means of measuring the CO₂ emissions of building materials is the calculation of their GWP through life cycle assessment (LCA). Analyzing the manufacture of construction materials is most analogous to a cradle-to-gate LCA, which evaluates the greenhouse gas emissions produced from raw material extraction (A1), transportation to the manufacturing site (A2), and the energy consumed and waste generated during the manufacturing process (A3) (Baumann & Tillman, 2004). For the purposes of this study, it is assumed that the materials (PC and nanocellulose) are manufactured separately and then shipped to the site for composite mixing beyond the gate. The water used in the preparation of PC with and without nanocellulose additives is assumed to be equal; therefore, it is not considered in this analysis. Further research, including testing of material performance, will be required to quantify the effect of nanocellulose additions on strength, durability, and recyclability before cradle-to-grave analyses of nanocellulose composite materials can be completed.

Cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment data used in the analysis of PC is from the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) procured by the Portland Cement Association (PCA) in 2021 (ASTM International, 2021). A review of data from 19 PC manufacturers that belong to PCA was conducted. This data represents about 64% of the total PC produced in the U.S. in 2019. The PC evaluated in this EPD is certified by ASTM International to meet the requirements of ASTM C219, C150, and C1157, as well as AASHTO M 85-20 and CSA A3001-13.

In the EPD, a functional unit of one metric ton is evaluated in stages A1-A3, as previously defined. Industry averages of material composition and clinker production technologies from 2019 data

provided by the 19 PC manufacturers included were used to calculate GWP in kg CO₂eq. Due to their negligible effect on the results, the impact of capital equipment and infrastructure, as well as personnel-related activities, were excluded from the analysis. For this study, GWP was calculated per kg of material from the results reported per metric ton.

EPDs are not currently available from nanocellulose manufacturers. Consequently, a literature review of cradle-to-gate life cycle assessments of nanocellulose from peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, and manufacturing reports was performed. The life cycle inventory (LCI) and LCA methods differed between data sources. The functional unit of each LCA was between 1 g and 1 kg. Thus, the GWP reported was converted to kg CO₂eq per kg of nanocellulose for this study. The small functional unit of these nanocellulose LCAs in comparison to the PC EPD highlights the large difference in the current production capacity of these materials. Scaling up this industry can lead to significant reductions in GWP, which is discussed in the conclusion.

The nanocellulose materials evaluated were produced from numerous raw material sources and processing methods. Hence, the results between LCAs represent different methods of raw material extraction, transportation, and manufacturing. The two types of nanocellulose considered, CNC and CNF, range in size from 5nm to 100nm in width, and 50nm to 20 μm in length, with aspect ratios between about 5 and 1000 (Moon et al., 2011b). Properties like strength, heat transfer, and methods of degradation also vary amongst them; thus, further research will be required to analyze the impact these properties have on sustainability in the use and end-of-life phases of their life cycles.

The carbon sequestered by biomaterials is an important aspect of their sustainability. Some LCAs of nanocellulose materials reported the effect of carbon sequestration on the GWP by analyzing the biogenic carbon of the material at hand. The resulting carbon emissions can be offset substantially by the carbon sequestration of biomaterials, which is reflected in the results of studies that considered it. Overall, this is a more realistic accounting of the CO₂ associated with materials; therefore, GWP results from LCAs that include biogenic carbon were used where applicable.

The GWP of manufacturing materials for a nanocellulose-PC composite material was calculated by first converting the kg CO₂eq/kg to kg CO₂eq/m³ for cement and each type of nanocellulose. Then, 0.2% of the resulting GWP/m³ for each type of nanocellulose was added to 99.8% of the resulting GWP/m³ for cement. This total GWP/m³ was then converted to GWP/kg of nanocellulose-PC composite using the appropriate composite density. The results amongst nanocellulose-PC composites were then compared.

Cost

The cost of PC and nanocellulose are documented in USD from sources online and price sheets from manufacturers. While PC production is industrialized and well-studied, data collected for nanocellulose is from lab-scale and small-scale industrial processes. Estimates for cost reductions from industry scale-up are thus presented in the conclusion.

Prices for PC vary between manufacturers, chemical compositions, and locations for shipping. For the purposes of this study, the industry average cost of cement in the United States in 2021 was used. Vendors provide nanocellulose in solids and in slurries, however pricing is usually listed on a dry weight basis. Cementitious materials require water for hydration, thus dry nanocellulose is not required, which is typically more expensive. Accordingly, the most affordable option was chosen between options for both CNC and CNF. This cost was converted to USD per kg of material for comparison between CNC and CNF, and vendors. These costs do not include the price of shipping to the manufacturing site.

The USD/m³ of each material was calculated using the density or specific gravity of that material. Then, 99.8% of the USD/m³ of PC was added to 0.2% of the USD/m³ of nanocellulose for each price point identified. The cost was then converted to USD/kg using the appropriate composite density to compare with the USD/kg of cement.

RESULTS

The GWP and cost of nanocellulose-PC composite materials are presented per kg for each combination of PC and nanocellulose reviewed. For nanocellulose materials with biogenic carbon considered in their LCAs, the results for GWP including biogenic carbon are displayed. These results are compared to 1 kg of PC for both GWP and cost, and the range of percentage difference between nanocellulose-PC composites and PC is presented.

Global Warming Potential

The GWP of nanocellulose materials from the reviewed cradle-to-gate LCA reports is summarized in Table 1. The type of nanocellulose, raw material source, and treatment type are displayed for comparison amongst sources, since the GWP is largely affected by the raw materials and processing methods used.

Table 1: Global warming potential (GWP) of nanocellulose per kg (GWP with biogenic carbon (GWP-BC) displayed where available)

Cellulose Type	Raw Material Source	Treatment Type	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg)	GWP-BC (kg CO ₂ eq/kg)	Reference	
CNC	Bleached Kraft Pulp	Sulfuric Acid Hydrolysis	29.64	N/A	(Gu et al., 2015)	
	Unripe Coconut Fiber	Chemical Acid Hydrolysis	1086.41	N/A	(de Figueirêdo et al., 2012)	
	White Cotton Fiber	Chemical Acid Hydrolysis	122.17	N/A		
	Thermomechanical Pulp		Sulfuric Acid Hydrolysis	31.70	N/A	(Zargar et al., 2022)
			DEC Pretreatment - Lignin Containing	12.90	N/A	
	Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch		Acid Hydrolysis & Chlorine	93.80	N/A	(Teh et al., 2019)
			Acid Hydrolysis	20.01	N/A	
			TEMPO-Oxidation	52.16	N/A	
CNF	Hardwood Kraft Pulp	Enzymatic treatments & Homogenization	18.60	N/A	(Gallo Stampino et al., 2021)	
	Industrial Waste Sludge	Enzymatic treatments & Homogenization	17.70	N/A		
	Cotton Linters	TEMPO-Oxidation & Homogenization	63.20	N/A		
	Industrial Waste Sludge	TEMPO-Oxidation & Homogenization	67.80	N/A		
	Cotton Linters	TEMPO-Oxidation & Ultrasonication	88.00	N/A		
	Industrial Waste Sludge	TEMPO-Oxidation & Ultrasonication	78.40	N/A		
	Wood Pulp		Enzymatic Pretreatment & Microfluidization	0.79	N/A	(Arvidsson et al., 2015)
			Carboxymethylation & Microfluidization	99.00	N/A	
			Homogenization	1.20	N/A	
	Wood Pulp		Grinding	7.60	5.76	(D. Moon et al., 2017)
	Wood Pulp		Milling & Hot Compressed Water - High Power	3.68	1.85	(Sun et al., 2013)
			Milling & Hot Compressed Water - Low Power	1.26	-0.57	

In general, there are two types of nanocellulose production: acid hydrolysis and mechanical grinding (Moon et al., 2011b). Both methods typically begin with kraft pulp, which is composed of larger cellulose fibers removed from plant material feedstocks, typically using acid hydrolysis. Nanocellulose is then extracted from the pulp, either with further acid hydrolysis, which breaks down the hemicellulosic and amorphous regions of cellulose, or by mechanical grinding, which separates the cellulose fibrils with applied shear forces. The other types of nanocellulose production reported here are TEMPO-oxidation and enzymatic pre-treatments, which also rely on the addition of chemicals to break down the cellulose fibers into nano-scale cellulosic materials.

As shown in Table 1, the minimum GWP per kg of nanocellulose reported is -0.57 kg CO₂eq, which is the result of a LCA of CNF produced from wood pulp with milling and compressed hot water using low power, with biogenic carbon considered (Sun et al., 2013). This result falls into the mechanical grinding category, in which the GWP is largely associated with the electricity required to produce the nanocellulose. The maximum GWP reported per kg of nanocellulose is 1086.41 kg CO₂eq, which is for CNC produced from unripe coconut fiber using acid hydrolysis (de Figueirêdo et al., 2012). This result did not consider the biogenic carbon of the resulting material.

The results from the PCA EPD in 2021 show that the cradle-to-gate industry average GWP of PC per kg is 0.922 kg CO₂eq. The manufacturing process of PC is highly industrialized with cement plants available throughout the United States. In contrast, each nanocellulose LCA reviewed had a different yield of nanocellulose from the raw material used, which depended on the cellulose content of the raw material and the preservation of that cellulose through production. This is representative of the current markets for both PC and nanocellulose and contributes to the wide range of results for GWP of nanocellulose-PC composites.

The results of the GWP per kg of nanocellulose-PC composites using results from each reviewed LCA are shown in Figure 1 below. The gray bars represent the GWP of 1 kg of plain PC (0.922 kg CO₂eq/kg) for comparison with the GWP of nanocellulose-PC composite materials (blue bars). In two nanocellulose-PC composites, a small reduction of GWP of 0.0001 kg CO₂eq/kg (-0.01%) and 0.0014 kg CO₂eq/kg (-0.15%) was found in comparison to the GWP of PC. The results of both of these LCAs of nanocellulose resulted from the evaluation of CNF produced from wood pulp; one study, however, evaluated a mechanical grinding process with low power (Sun et al., 2013), while the other evaluated an enzymatic pre-treatment process with microfluidization (Arvidsson et al., 2015). The rest of the results display an increase in GWP between 0.0003 kg CO₂eq (0.03%) and 1.105 kg CO₂eq (119.72%), resulting from various raw material sources and production processes.

Global Warming Potential (GWP) of Nanocellulose-PC Composites

Figure 1: Global warming potential (GWP) of nanocellulose-PC composites per kg (GWP of PC = 0.922 kg CO₂eq/kg)

In summary, based on the results of lab and small-scale production of nanocellulose materials, the addition of nanocellulose to cement by 0.2% volume reduces the total GWP of Portland cement in two scenarios by less than 1%. In most cases, adding nanocellulose to the cement paste increases the GWP of the resulting composite by between 0.03% and 13.37%. In one case, the GWP of PC is increased by 119.72%, which is much higher than the results of any other study observed. Disregarding this outlier, the average difference in GWP per kg of composite material in comparison to plain PC is an increase of 4.41%.

Cost

The cost per kg of each type of nanocellulose reviewed is shown in Table 2, not including the price of shipping to the site. It should be noted that these vendors typically produce about 1 ton of nanocellulose per batch, or less. In comparison to PC, which is produced in several metric tons per batch, this is a very small-scale production process. These costs reflect the market in 2022 for small purchases of cellulose nanomaterials per gram.

Table 2: Nanocellulose cost per kg for CNC and CNF

Cellulose Type	Vendor				
	1	2	3	4	5
CNC	\$1,000.00	\$661.39	\$100.00	\$864.45	\$950.33
CNF	-	\$165.35	-	\$897.22	\$986.49

The price per kg of CNC ranges from \$50 USD to \$1,000 USD, while the price of CNF ranges from \$165.35 USD to \$986.49 USD, without shipping and handling costs. According to Statista, the average cost of cement in United States for 2021 was \$125 per metric ton (Garside, 2022). The average cost per kg of PC in the U.S. is therefore \$0.13, not considering shipment to the site. The costs of nanocellulose-PC composites are shown in Figure 2. The increase in cost of the nanocellulose-PC composites compared to PC ranges from 43.49% to 836.84%. On average, the addition of 0.2% volume nanocellulose to PC increases the cost by 570.37% of that of plain PC.

Figure 2: Cost of nanocellulose-PC composites per kg for each vendor evaluated, 1-5 (cost of PC = \$0.13 per kg)

DISCUSSION

Cementitious materials will most likely continue to be an important construction resource for the foreseeable future due to their ubiquitous availability, structural performance, and cost. Regardless, there remains a need to reduce the total environmental impact that PC has around the globe, and supplementing it with more sustainable materials while maintaining, and even enhancing, its mechanical properties is possible. This study demonstrated that the addition of nanocellulose from small-scale production can reduce the GWP of PC with certain raw material feedstocks and processing techniques, especially when biogenic carbon is considered, but increases the GWP with others. The cost of PC, on the other hand, is significantly increased by nanocellulose additions across the board when considering the current market for both materials. The production capacity of nanocellulose has a lot of room to grow; thus, the results presented here, including cost and GWP, will be impacted by future improvements to nanocellulose processing capabilities.

Scaling up nanocellulose production reportedly has the potential to significantly reduce its GWP and cost. For example, the Forest Products Laboratory (FPL) evaluated their pilot line of CNC production

in 2015. At the pilot plant scale, sulfuric acid is neutralized by the addition of sodium hydroxide before being released into the waste stream, which is the largest contributor to its environmental impact in their life cycle assessment. At the industrial scale, they estimated that these chemicals could be recycled, which could reduce the overall GWP of the CNCs produced. Specifically, 50% of the GWP was attributed to chemicals, which could be reduced by 90% through recycling, and 25% of the GWP was attributed to electricity use, which could be reduced by 50% at a higher scale of production (Gu et al., 2015).

Additionally, not all studies of nanocellulose discuss the biogenic carbon associated with this natural, renewable material. Biogenic carbon considerations are essential to a sustainable future in the manufacturing of materials. An accurate representation of the embodied carbon associated with a material should include all inputs and outputs of CO₂eq throughout its lifecycle. During the growth of biomaterial feedstocks, the sequestration of carbon removes existing CO₂ from the atmosphere, thereby subtracting GWP from the total carbon accounting of the material. Overall, the growth of biomaterials, and the incentive to grow more biomass in the future, can reduce the amount of greenhouse gas emissions in the atmosphere. Thus, it is important to understand the entire life cycle of materials, including carbon sequestration and agricultural processes, when evaluating the GWP of biomaterials.

Furthermore, de Assis, et. al. estimated the cost reduction of scaling up the pilot production of CNF at University of Maine in 2017. They found that the minimum product selling price could be reduced by 37% by scaling the facility from 1 ton per day of production to 50 tons per day of production, with the use of specific feedstocks and co-location manufacturing facilities (de Assis et al., 2018). The cost and GWP reported in this study are true to the current conditions of the market for CNC and CNF, and their small-scale production causes a large variation in the data. However, scaling up the production of these materials is happening, and future studies will be required to assess how cost and GWP will be affected by these changes in the market.

Finally, the addition of nanocellulose to cement has an impact on structural strength, which can reduce the total amount of material required for a given loading condition. The durability of cement can also be improved, potentially reducing the GWP and cost of concrete in the use phase through reduction of materials and energy needed for maintenance and repair. This could also improve the quality of materials for reuse in the end-of-life phase. Therefore, cradle-to-grave analyses will be required to capture the full effect of nanocellulose additions on the GWP and cost of nanocellulose-PC composite materials in the future.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that the addition of nanocellulose to Portland cement can decrease or increase the total GWP of the resulting composite material, depending on the type of nanocellulose used, when considering only the manufacturing of materials. It was also found that the addition of nanocellulose to PC can significantly increase its cost per kg based on the current market prices of nanocellulose from small-batch facilities. These results could be significantly affected, however, by the enhanced performance of nanocellulose-PC composites in comparison to plain PC; thus, cradle-to-grave analyses considering the strength and durability of the materials will be required in the future to fully understand the effect of nanocellulose additions to the economic and environmental performance of nanocellulose-PC composite materials.

Specifically, the difference in the GWP of nanocellulose-PC composites was calculated to be between -0.15% and 119.72% of the GWP of plain PC (4.41% on average disregarding the outlier). A reduction in GWP was found using the results from two LCAs, both of which evaluated CNF derived from wood pulp (Arvidsson et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2013). This is likely due to the high yield of cellulose from wood in comparison to other biomass resources, like coconut fiber and industrial waste streams. The methods used for processing the biomass can also affect the GWP. One of the GWP-reducing nanocellulose LCAs examined a mechanical grinding process (Sun et al., 2013), and the other examined an enzymatic pre-treatment and microfluidization process (Arvidsson et al., 2015).

The nanocellulose with the highest GWP was produced using acid hydrolysis (de Figueirêdo et al., 2012). The processing method is not always indicative of the magnitude of the GWP though, and there was no obvious trend observed between mechanical grinding and acid hydrolysis processes in this study. The cost, on the other hand, was always increased by the addition of nanocellulose. From prices currently listed by the vendors identified in this study, the cost of nanocellulose-PC composites was increased between 43.49% and 836.84% per kg of composite material (570.37% on average) when compared to PC.

The variation in these results can be at least partially attributed to the variability associated with small-scale production, as well as the difference in raw materials and processing methods used in each study. The lowest and highest cost are both represented by CNC materials, and CNF materials show a similar variation in pricing. The largest increase in GWP resulted from processing coconut fiber into nanocellulose. Coconut fiber has a high lignin content and therefore a low yield of nanocellulose per unit amount of bulk material. The isolation of the nanocellulose from the bulk material thus requires a high expenditure of resources, resulting in a large production of CO₂ emissions per kg of nanocellulose produced (de Figueirêdo et al., 2012). Consequently, the chemical composition of the biomaterial feedstock used is an important consideration when attempting to reduce the GWP of nano-cellulosic end products.

Further research will be required to identify the specific effects of scaling up the production of nanocellulose on the GWP and cost of nanocellulose-PC composite materials. Furthermore, as more sustainable cement mixes are gaining popularity over PC, alternative and supplementary cementitious materials need to be considered for a more comprehensive evaluation of the GWP and cost of different types of concrete with nanocellulose additives. Additionally, testing will be required to measure the effect of nanocellulose additions on the strength and durability of cementitious materials, depending on the physical and mechanical properties of the nanocellulose used. These measurements can then be utilized in cradle-to-grave life cycle analyses and life cycle costing of nanocellulose-PC materials for a full understanding of the economic and environmental impact of nanocellulose additives in Portland cement, and other cementitious mixes.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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